

ducks — possess limitations and have been used only in certain regions, and breeding for insect resistance is in its infancy. ■

Gall midge life cycle and plant injury in South China

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In Kwangtung Province, South China, the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* undergoes 9–10 overlapping generations a year to cause its greatest damage to the third irrigated rice crop. A life cycle is completed in 21–38 days.

The larvae feeding within the culm base cause the formation of galls or silver shoots. It is not clear whether feeding activity or a salivary gland substance by the maggot stimulates growth to form a gall. Gall formation is caused by the suppression of leaf primordial differentiation in the growing point and the development of radial ridges from the innermost leaf primordium, followed by leaf sheath elongation. This occurs in the tillering stage. After panicle initiation, larvae no longer cause damage because the growing point has changed (see figure). ■

Stage	Duration (days)	Status of gall formation	Diagram showing gall formation	Average length (mm) of the gall	Outer appearance of the rice plant	Type of gall
1st-instar larvae	Early period 1–3	Newly hatched larvae entering the growing point 1				
	Middle period 3–4	Oval-shaped chamber formed by the inner young leaf 2				
	Late period 5–6	Multiplication and thickening of the cells on the upper layer of the oval-shaped chamber 3				
2d-instar larvae	Primary period 0.5	Multiplication and thickening of the sponge-shaped cells in the ova-shaped chamber 4		1.6		
	Middle & late period 1–1.5	A gall has completely formed 5			Features of type A galls: 1. The leaves turn deep green and become harder and stand straight. 2. No heart leaf, or the heart leaf shortened. 3. The distance of auricle from the top leaf gets longer, the angle of leaf blade tends to extend, resulting in abnormal growth of the blade. 4. The base of the plant markedly swells.	
3d-instar larvae	3–4	The length of the gall is equal to that of the insect body 6				
Pre-pupa	2	The gall begins to elongate 7		5.5		
Duration of pupae	1st stage pupae 1.4	The gall markedly elongates		9	Features of type B galls: The galls elongate.	
	2d stage pupae 1.4			28		
	3d stage pupae 1.4			53		
	4th stage pupae 1.4	96				
	5th stage pupae 1.4	The gall elongates very rapidly	105			

Diagram showing the process of gall formation and the characteristics of the injury due to the rice gall midge. Observations were made on the injury of rice seedlings by 3d generation of rice gall midge in Du-yan Commune, Sin-hui County, Kwangtung Province, China, 1976.

Ants — a natural enemy of *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* larvae in dryland rice

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In dryland areas of Batangas province, Philippines, where 1 crop of rice/year is grown, the leaf folder *Chaphalocrosis medinalis* (Guenee) is the most important insect pest attacking the aboveground portions of the rice plant. But investigation of folded leaves in the 1978 season revealed very few larvae. Possible explanations were sought through field observations. Ants were found to leave their nests in underground tunnels and

Adult of *Diacamma* sp. [120 X](Hymenoptera:Formicidae). IIRI.